

Exploring the Antibacterial Effects of Pine Honey

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Abstract :

The purpose of this study was to evaluate the antibacterial efficacy of pine honey against *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), with the goal of establishing a scientific basis for its traditional use and explore its potential as an alternative antimicrobial agent. While honey is generally used as a natural sweetener, it is recognized for its many therapeutic properties and as a remedy for various ailments. Despite the recognized therapeutic applications of various honeys, especially notable in Manuka honey's effectiveness against pathogens like *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Helicobacter pylori*, pine honey's specific antibacterial potential remains less explored. This research aimed to provide support for its traditional use in treating bacterial infections and to assess its viability as an alternative antimicrobial treatment. The experiment involved testing various concentrations of pine honey on nutrient agar plates inoculated with *E. coli*. Contrary to the anticipated antibacterial activity based on pine honey's traditional uses and the general antimicrobial properties of honey, the results indicated no inhibition of *E. coli* growth at any concentration. This unexpected outcome suggests that pine honey, despite its rich mineral content and antioxidants, may lack sufficient antibacterial compounds like hydrogen peroxide, methylglyoxal, and bee defensin-1, which are important in other honeys for combating bacterial infections. Further research testing different conditions, concentrations, and honey types need to be done to fully understand the scope and limitations of pine honey as an antimicrobial agent.

Keywords : Pine Honey, antimicrobial, *E. coli* resistance, Antibacterial

Introduction :

Honey has been a widely relied on substance, not only as a natural sweetener, but also as a remedy for various kinds of ailments and infections due to its therapeutic properties. Particularly, the effects through its antimicrobial attributes, have been a well documented form of information, which highlights the potential of honey to be utilized as an effective agent against bacterial infections. Primarily attributed to its enzymatic production of hydrogen peroxide, its high osmolarity content, and the presence of specific bioactive compounds, the contents of the various types of honey continues to be studied, in order to determine the effectiveness in its abilities (Mandal & Mandal, 2011). Among various types of honey, Manuka honey has been one of the most extensively studied honeys and is renowned for its potent antimicrobial properties, attributed to the unique Manuka factor (UMF). This type of honey is noted to take on antimicrobial action against pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus* (*S. aureus*) and *Helicobacter pylori* (*H. pylori*) (Mandal & Mandal, 2011). These studies provide a precedent for exploring the antibacterial potential of other less-studied types of honey.

Specifically, pine honey, also known as forest honey or honeydew honey, is a unique variety of honey that differs significantly from the more common honeys that are secreted from floral

nectar. Rather, the pine honey results from the secretions of sap-feeding insects on pine trees, imbuing the honey with unique phytochemical properties, potentially affecting its antibacterial activity. Pine honey is darker, less sweet, and has a stronger, more aromatic in flavor compared to floral honeys, while also including a higher mineral content and a rich array of antioxidants, such as flavonoids and phenolic acids. The history of pine honey goes hand in hand with the regions of its production. In the areas of Greece, Turkey, and Italy, pine honey has been collected for centuries and is integral to its local economies and culinary traditions. Historically, it has been utilized for centuries as a natural remedy due to its antibacterial, antiviral, and antifungal properties (Tsavea et al., 2022). It has been traditionally used to alleviate sore throats and coughs, as well as to treat minor burns, cuts, and various bacterial infections (Eteraf-Oskouei & Najafi, 2013). Despite its extensive utilization as natural medicine across the Mediterranean, pine honey has not been as extensively investigated as other types of honey, such as Manuka honey.

This study aims to uncover the inhibitory effects of Pine honey on *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*), a common bacterial pathogen responsible for various infections, in order to gain valuable insights to further establish a scientific basis for its traditional uses. The selection of *E. coli* as a test organism also allows for comparisons with the effects observed with other honeys, thereby contributing to a broader understanding of honey's antimicrobial properties. Based on the previous extensive research and literature of honey inhibition, and the antibacterial properties that honey possesses, it can be anticipated that the pine honey will be successful in its inhibition of *E. coli*.

Methodology :

As this experiment relies on nutrient agar plates for the inoculation with *E. coli*, the preparation of the Nutrient agar plates is necessary to proceed. This is done by measuring 3.0 gm of LB Broth (Luria-Bertani), and adding it into the 180 mL of autoclaved water. Set this aside, and acquire 150 mL of autoclaved 3% Agar in water. Set the 3% Agar in water inside of a microwave, with a loose lid attachment, for a consistent repetition of approximately 10 seconds to slowly turn the 3% Agar in water into liquid. Every 10 seconds, swirl the container, and place it back into the microwave to continue its melting. Once the 3% Agar in water is fully turned into a liquid, place it aside to slightly cool off, and take the LB Broth and 180 mL of autoclaved water mixture and place it into the microwave for 6 minutes. Once the 6 minutes is complete, be sure to check that the 3% Agar in water is still a liquid by carefully swirling it, and pour the LB Broth and 180 mL of autoclaved water mixture into the 3% Agar in water constantly swirling the container. Once combined, this mixture will be able to prepare up to 12 individual plates. Quickly but carefully pour in the mixture into the three sets of 4 stacked plates so it evenly coats the surface of the plate, instantly cover, and repeat for all 12 plates. Allow the plates to form for 24-36 hours, and use soon after preparation. .

To begin this experiment, start by acquiring the pine honey and preparing a stock solution that will be used for all of the intended honey concentrations. In this case, the concentrations will be 5 ml, 10 ml, 15 ml, and the control group, which must be 0 ml. The positive control will be water without any honey in it, while the negative control group will be the broth containing the bacteria. Calculate each concentration's quantity in order to understand how much Pine honey and sterile water will be required. The calculation is done using equation 1.

Eq 1: Mass of honey (g)=Volume of solution (ml)×Desired concentration (% w/v)/100.

For example, to prepare 100 ml of a 1% w/v solution, use 1 g of honey and 99 ml of sterile water. In order to measure the honey, a balance will be used to measure the required amount of Pine honey for each concentration. Place a sterile container on the balance, set the balance to zero, and add honey until the desired calculated mass is reached. Go on to transfer the measured honey into a larger sterile beaker or flask. Add the calculated amount of sterile distilled water to the honey. For the positive control solution, only use sterile water and do not add any honey. Once both quantities are measured and combined in one sterile beaker or flask, thoroughly mix the honey and water to ensure a homogenous solution. This can be achieved manually by stirring with a sterile stir bar. Continue mixing until the honey is completely dissolved in the water. (This may take some time, especially for higher concentrations of honey.) After the honey is fully dissolved, check the volume of the solution. If necessary, adjust it to the final desired volume by adding more sterile water, as some volume might have been lost during stirring. Once the solutions are ready, transfer it to the experimental setup. (If not used immediately, cover the containers and store them at 4°C to prevent contamination. Ensure the containers are tightly sealed to avoid evaporation and concentration changes. Be sure to repeat this process for each desired concentration of Pine honey, as well as for both control solutions.

The inoculation of agar plates is done in order to make note of any consistent bacterial growth across the plate, such as antimicrobial susceptibility testing. Preparation of the workspace is critical to maintain aseptic conditions, therefore begin with cleaning the workspace with a disinfectant and organizing all required materials, so as to not move from space to space more than necessary. Using a cell spreader, submerge the tool into a beaker of ethanol and proceed to pass it through the flame of a Bunsen burner or alcohol lamp until it catches a flame. Immediately remove the cell spreader from the flame and allow for the flame to go out on its own to sterilize it. Allow it to cool for a few seconds before proceeding. Using a micropipette, dispense 100 microliters of the prepared E. coli, MV10Nal suspension onto the center of the solidified agar surface in each plate and use the cell spreader to evenly distribute the bacterial suspension across the entire surface of the agar. Be sure to rotate the plate as the cell spreader moves in swift circular motions to ensure a thin coating of bacteria in order for it to grow into a uniform lawn. Once the entire surface has been inoculated, immediately close the agar plate to

minimize exposure to airborne contaminants. Invert the plate (to prevent condensation from dripping onto the agar surface) and place it in an incubator set at 37°C. The incubation period requires 24-48 hours. After incubation, examine the plate for a uniform lawn of bacterial growth. This will indicate a successful inoculation and the plate is ready for subsequent experimental steps.

Applying the Pine honey solutions to the agar plates will test their antibacterial activity against *E. coli*. Label each agar plate with the concentration of the Pine honey or the type of control (positive or negative) that will be applied to the paper discs inside the agar plate. There will be four discs placed inside of the plates, each containing 5 ml, 10 ml, 15 ml, and the control group of 0 ml of the Pine honey solution. This will ensure a clear system of identifying where each solution will be placed and minimize any confusion between the varying concentrations of Pine honey. If using forceps to handle the paper discs, sterilize them by dipping in alcohol and passing through a flame. Allow them to cool before picking up a disc. On a separate plate, be sure to add a thin layer of the LB broth stock solution before applying the honey soaked discs. The application of each of the honey solutions will require a direct application using a sterile pipette to draw up a small volume of the first Pine honey solution. Using this, gently spot the solution onto a designated area of the agar surface. Usually, 5-10 μL is sufficient, but ensure to use the same volume for all samples. Using the cooled, sterilized forceps, place a honey-soaked disc onto the agar surface in its designated spot. Apply gentle pressure to ensure full contact with the agar but avoid penetrating the agar surface. Go on to apply a drop of sterile water using a new pipette tip or a sterile water-soaked disc as the positive control to one of the designated spots on the agar plate. Similarly, apply your negative control to another designated spot on the plate.

After all the applications of the ranging honey solution concentrations, including the controls, are completed, incubate the agar plates inverted at 37°C for 24 hours. Once the incubation period is complete, examine the plates for zones of inhibition around each application point or disc, as these zones are an indication of where bacterial growth has been inhibited by the Pine honey or control substances.

Further observation and measurement of growth will be carried out using a spectrophotometer. This instrument measures the absorbance or transmittance of a sample at specific wavelengths of light. To begin, resuspension of the bacteria is required in order to measure the absorbance of this liquid culture. Followed by the incubation, use a sterile loop or swab to gently scrape the bacterial lawn from the agar surface, focusing on areas around and including the inhibition zones. Suspend the collected bacteria in a known volume of sterile saline or PBS in a sterile tube. Be sure to stay consistent across all samples to ensure comparability. Vortex the suspension for a few seconds for an even distribution of bacteria in the solution. Turn on the spectrophotometer and allow it to warm up. Set the spectrophotometer to measure absorbance at a wavelength of 610 nm, as this range strikes a balance between sensitivity and specificity for bacterial cells.

Calibrate the spectrophotometer using sterile saline or PBS as a blank to set the baseline absorbance to zero. Measure the absorbance of each bacterial suspension. Record all of the values. In order to properly interpret the results, make note that higher absorbance values indicate a higher concentration of bacteria in the suspension, reflecting greater bacterial growth from the agar plate area sampled. Therefore, Compare the absorbance values between samples treated with different concentrations of Pine honey, the negative control with sterile water, and the positive control. The positive control is expected to have the highest absorbance due to having the least inhibited bacterial growth.

The data analysis will involve comparing the inhibition zones and calculating the percent inhibition across different honey concentrations. Begin by gathering all of the recorded measurements of the inhibition zones for each Pine honey concentration, including the control groups. If replicas for each concentration have been conducted, calculate the average size of the inhibition zones for each Pine honey concentration to reduce variability in your data. Using a graph, plot the average inhibition zone sizes against the concentrations of Pine honey, as a visual representation can help identify trends and the concentration-response relationship. To calculate the percent inhibition for each concentration, use equation 2.

$$\text{Eq 2: Percent Inhibition} = \left(\frac{\text{Inhibition Zone of Control} - \text{Inhibition Zone of Sample}}{\text{Inhibition Zone of Control}} \right) \times 100$$

For this calculation, the "Inhibition Zone of Control" refers to the diameter around the positive control, assuming it produces the largest zone of inhibition. If using sterile water as the control, which should not produce an inhibition zone, go on to calculate the percent effectiveness relative to the positive control using Equation 3.

$$\text{Eq 3: Percent Effectiveness} = \left(\frac{\text{Inhibition Zone of Sample}}{\text{Inhibition Zone of Positive Control}} \right) \times 100$$

The equation above assumes the inhibition zone produced by the positive control as the baseline for 100% effectiveness. The resulting percent effectiveness for each Pine honey concentration indicates its antibacterial activity relative to the known effectiveness of the positive control.

If following Equation 2, interpret the calculated percent inhibition and correlation coefficient to assess the antibacterial effectiveness of Pine honey. Determine which concentration of Pine honey shows the most significant antibacterial effect against E. coli. Look for a dose-response relationship, where higher concentrations of Pine honey result in larger inhibition zones. Discuss any trends or patterns observed in the data. If following Equation 3, make note of the concentrations of Pine honey that yield higher percent effectiveness scores, as these are more

effective in inhibiting *E. coli* growth, as indicated by their ability to produce larger inhibition zones compared to the positive control.

Results :

Figure 1: Plated *E. coli* Bacteria with Submerged Discs of Varying Concentrations.

Figure 1 displays an even lawn of the *E. coli*, MV10Nal across the agar plate with four outlined quadrants to signify each varying concentration of pine honey, exposed to each paper disc. There is no site of inhibition surrounding any of the discs in the quadrants. In the 0 ml quadrant, there is no inhibition or significant growth of bacteria surrounding the disc. The 5 ml quadrant demonstrates a very thin margin of growth of the bacteria surrounding the disc. The 10 ml quadrant visually has the most site of bacterial growth around the paper disc. The 15 ml quadrant demonstrates bacterial growth, over top and to the sides of the paper disc.

Figure 2: Plated *E. coli* Bacteria (Agar Top) with Submerged Discs of Varying Concentrations.

Figure 2 displays an even lawn of the *E. coli*, MV10Nal across the agar plate with an additional agar broth solution coated on top. There are four outlined quadrants to signify each varying concentration of pine honey exposed to each paper disc. There is no visual site of inhibition surrounding any of the discs in any of the quadrants. In the 0 ml quadrant, there is no inhibition or any growth of bacteria surrounding the disc. The 5 ml quadrant demonstrates a very slight amount of growth of the bacteria surrounding the disc. The 10 ml quadrant has a slight more amount of bacterial growth than the 5 ml quadrant, but not that much greater. The 15 ml quadrant demonstrates the most bacterial growth, to the sides of the paper disc.

Discussion :

The antibacterial properties of pine honey against *Escherichia coli* were tested using nutrient agar plates. Despite the antimicrobial properties previously attributed to various types of honey, the results showed no inhibition of bacterial growth at any of the tested concentrations of pine honey. This outcome may be attributed to several potential factors that could explain the absence of the expected antibacterial effect.

The nature of pine honey could be a fundamental reason for the lack of inhibition. Unlike floral honeys, pine honey is primarily derived from honeydew and may contain fewer antibacterial compounds such as hydrogen peroxide, methylglyoxal, and bee defensin-1. These compounds are thought to be key antimicrobial agents in other types of honey (Nolan, Harrison, & Cox, 2019). The chemical composition of pine honey, influenced by its lower acidity and different enzymatic content, (Tsavea et al., 2022) may not be as suppressive to the growth of *E. coli*. Additionally, variations in the bioactivity of pine honey may come from specific environmental conditions from which it was produced, which can affect its phytochemical profile (Zammit Young & Blundell, 2023).

The lack of antibacterial activity observed could be further understood by considering additional biological and environmental factors influencing both the honey and the bacteria. One potential factor is the specific strain of *E. coli* used in the experiment. Various strains of *E. coli* possess different levels of virulence and resistance mechanisms, which might inherently make them more resilient against certain types of antimicrobial agents, including natural products such as honey. Some strains have been observed to possess efflux pumps that actively expel antimicrobial compounds from the cell, or protective biofilms that shield the bacterial colony from harmful agents (Gaurav et al., 2023)(Ito et al., 2009). These biofilms are particularly resistant to penetration by antibacterial substances by forming a physical barrier that prevents antibacterial agents from reaching the bacterial cells.

The enzyme content of pine honey may also influence its antibacterial efficacy. Enzymes like glucose oxidase, which are more prevalent in other types of honey, catalyze the production of hydrogen peroxide, (Brudzynski, 2020) a well-known antimicrobial agent. The lower enzyme activity in pine honey may result in insufficient production of hydrogen peroxide, reducing its ability to inhibit bacterial growth. In addition, the overall lower antioxidant properties of pine honey compared to other darker honeys may also contribute to its reduced antibacterial effectiveness, as antioxidants have been shown to disrupt the bacterial cell growth process (Suriyaprom et al., 2022).

Human error and experimental limitations also may have contributed to the results showing a lack of inhibition. Error in the preparation and handling of the honey solutions, such as incorrect measurement or improper mixing, may have led to ineffective concentrations. Additionally, the technique used for inoculating the agar plates may have influenced the outcomes. An uneven distribution of the *E. coli* or improper application of the honey solutions could prevent adequate contact between the honey and the bacteria, nullifying any potential inhibitory effects.

Environmental and systematic errors during the experimental setup may have contributed to the findings. If the pine honey or agar plates were not properly handled, their growth would not be properly assessed. If the honey had antibacterial properties initially, exposure to high temperatures or light may have degraded them. The pH and nutrient composition of the agar may have had an impact on the effectiveness of the antibacterial agents in the honey. A high nutrient composition may have resulted in the bacteria growing too quickly, resulting in the honey not having enough time to inhibit growth. Alternatively, the nutrient composition of the agar used may have provided *E. coli* with sufficient resources to counteract the inhibitory effects of the honey. Agar rich nutrients could increase the bacteria's defense mechanisms, enabling them to thrive despite the presence of antimicrobial agents. Inconsistencies with incubation conditions such as the temperature not being properly calibrated or maintained may have altered the bacterial growth and interaction with the honey.

Future experiments may lead to different results with several changes being implemented. Higher concentrations of pine honey may lead to a more effective inhibition. Altering the growth rate of the *E. coli* may increase the chance of inhibition. This can be done by lowering the nutrient dose in the medium itself. Testing a different type of bacteria or variant of *E. coli* may provide insight on bacterial resistance. Utilizing a variety of honey types, particularly those known for their strong antimicrobial properties, such as Manuka honey, may also provide comparative insights and help validate the specific influence of pine honey. Further studies should focus on a broader spectrum of experimental modifications and explore the mechanistic aspects of honey's antibacterial action. Investigating how different types of honey interact with the bacterial cell structures. Additionally, expanding the range of tested bacteria might reveal whether the lack of inhibition observed with *E. coli* is an isolated case or indicative of a broader trend. Long-term studies assessing the stability of honey's antibacterial properties and the effects of storage conditions could also help in understanding its potential as a natural antimicrobial agent. Conducting genomic studies on the bacterial strains used could reveal specific genes associated with resistance to natural antimicrobials. Additionally, biochemical assays to assess the actual concentration of antimicrobial agents like hydrogen peroxide and other active compounds in the pine honey used could provide insights into whether the honey's intrinsic properties were sufficient to exert an antibacterial effect.

While the current experiment did not demonstrate the antibacterial efficacy of pine honey against *E. coli*, it shows the importance of considering both the biochemical characteristics of the honey and the methodological aspects of antibacterial testing. These findings lead the way for further studies into the conditions under which pine honey could be effective, offering insights for the application of natural products in antimicrobial therapies.

Conclusion :

The findings from this experiment, which tested the antibacterial properties of pine honey against *Escherichia coli*, revealed no inhibition of bacterial growth across all tested concentrations. This outcome leads to an analysis of the properties of pine honey and the experimental methodologies used. Unlike other honeys that are known for their robust antimicrobial effects, pine honey contains lower levels of key antimicrobial compounds such as hydrogen peroxide, methylglyoxal, and bee defensin-1. This compositional difference likely contributes to its diminished effectiveness against *E. coli*, a bacterium that can exhibit varied resistance mechanisms such as efflux pumps and protective biofilms.

The experimental approach may have influenced the results, with potential errors stemming from the preparation of the honey solutions or inaccurate measurements. Additionally, the method of applying these solutions to the agar plates might not have facilitated effective contact with the bacteria, further diminishing the potential for observable inhibition. The honey or agar plates being exposed to suboptimal conditions may also have led to degradation of its antibacterial components. Moreover, the nutrient-rich environment of the agar used might have provided *E. coli* with enough resources to overcome the inhibitory effects of the honey, suggesting that modifications in the nutrient composition of the medium could be necessary for future tests.

Future research should consider testing higher concentrations of pine honey, using honeys with different biochemical profiles, and employing more controlled and precise methodologies to ensure consistent application and measurement. Using other bacterial strains or changing specific environmental conditions such as temperature may also provide insight on the specific contexts in which pine honey may be effective.

While this study did not demonstrate the efficacy of pine honey against *E. coli*, it highlights the importance of detailed methodological planning and the need to understand the biochemical properties of natural products in antimicrobial research. These findings may be used to plan further investigations into the potential of pine honey and other natural substances in combating bacterial infections, emphasizing the complexity of natural product application in antimicrobial therapies.

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